

Impact of automated and manual segmentation errors on knee osteoarthritis classification using MRI-registered data on CT scans[☆]

Sydney Fox^{a,1}, Federica Kiyomi Ciliberti^{a,*,1}, Halldór Jónsson Jr.^a, Paolo Gargiulo^{a,b,2}, Marco Recenti^{a,2}

^a Institute of Biomedical and Neural Engineering, Reykjavik University, Menntavegur 1, 102, Reykjavik, Iceland

^b Department of Science, Landspítali University Hospital, Skafatilhöf 24, 105, Reykjavik, Iceland

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ABSTRACT

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is a prevalent, disabling disease for which early, accurate diagnosis is essential to guide treatment and reduce long-term burden. Machine learning (ML) approaches using quantitative imaging biomarkers show promise for automated OA classification, but their reliability under imperfect image segmentation remains unclear. This study evaluated the robustness of cartilage-based radiodensity and morphological features derived from MRI-registered CT scans against simulated segmentation errors. Manual segmentations of femoral, patellar, lateral tibial, and medial tibial cartilages were modified using morphological operations (erosion, dilation, and closing) to imitate automated and manual segmentation inaccuracies. A total of 130 knee scans (79 control, 51 degenerative) were analyzed. Several ML models, including tree-based models and support vector classifiers (SVC) with different kernels, were trained and tested using nested cross-validation. Statistical analyses confirmed that cartilage density variation and medial tibial cartilage volume and surface area remained significant discriminators despite pixel perturbations. Among ML models, SVC with radial basis kernel (RBF SVC) achieved the highest performance on the original dataset (F1 0.86, ROC AUC 0.91), with Linear and RBF SVC and Logistic Regression performing comparably under error-modified datasets (F1 between 0.80 and 0.86, ROC AUC between 0.86 and 0.92). While tree-based models were more sensitive to dilation errors, most models maintained weighted F1 scores ≥ 0.75 . These findings demonstrate that ML classifiers can robustly distinguish degenerative from control knees even when cartilage masks are imprecisely segmented. Thus, highly precise manual segmentations may not be strictly required for reliable OA classification, suggesting potential for scalable and cost-effective deployment of ML-based diagnostic tools in clinical imaging workflows.

1. Introduction

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is a multi-faceted disease of knee joint disorders involving articular cartilage, subchondral bone, ligaments, and synovial membranes. However, it is primarily characterized by knee cartilage degeneration which results mostly from nontraumatic daily activity (Hsu and Siwiec, 2024; Martel-Pelletier et al., 2016). Knee OA is a progressive disease, and the symptoms suffered by individuals diagnosed with knee OA are debilitating and negatively impact quality of life. Primary clinical symptoms of knee OA include pain and tenderness that is gradually onset, worse with prolonged, repetitive activity or inactivity, knee stiffness and swelling, and decreased mobility (Hsu

and Siwiec, 2024; Geng et al., 2023). Some of these clinical symptoms, namely chronic pain and limited mobility, significantly contribute to depression, anxiety, and sleep disturbances related to pain and physical limitations brought about by OA (Pickering et al., 2016). Other physical indications include visual swelling, quadriceps muscle atrophy, crepitus sounds during movement, limited joint range of motion, and valgus or varus deformities (Hsu and Siwiec, 2024; Geng et al., 2023).

Osteoarthritis affects an estimated 595 million individuals worldwide. Knee OA is by far the most common type of OA diagnosed globally, comprising over 50 percent of age-standardized OA presence, and estimates suggest there will be 642 million individuals diagnosed with knee OA by 2050 (Steinmetz et al., 2023). Knee OA has an

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* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: federicac@ru.is (F.K. Ciliberti).

¹ These authors share first authorship.

² These authors share last authorship.

estimated 13 percent prevalence in women and 10 percent prevalence in men aged 60 and above, rising to nearly 40 percent for all at age 70 (Hsu and Siwiec, 2024; Steinmetz et al., 2023). Even with only 15 to 50 percent of patients with radiological knee OA diagnoses reporting symptomatic pain, the disease accounts for 12.1 million years lived with disability (YLD) worldwide, 1.4 percent of the global total YLD (Leifer et al., 2022; Hsu and Siwiec, 2024; Martel-Pelletier et al., 2016).

OA presents a significant financial burden on healthcare systems throughout the world. The estimated cost of OA ranges from €1.8 to 4.7 billion annually across European nations (Prieto-Alhambra et al., 2014; Hallberg et al., 2023). Around the world, patients with knee OA spend an average of 700–15,600 USD annually treating and managing the disease, with an average of 140,300 USD in estimated lifetime costs (Leifer et al., 2022; Losina et al., 2015). Knee OA is a particularly costly form of OA. Guideline-accordant treatment for knee OA can comprise an average of 12,400 ± 9000 USD additional cost compared to control groups with similar demographic and clinical characteristics, with knee replacement surgery averaging 21,930 USD and subsequent pain management interventions averaging 560–740 USD annually (Losina et al., 2015; Leifer et al., 2022).

1.1. Disease progression and interventions

Knee OA is a progressive disease with no known current disease-modifying or curable agents (Geng et al., 2023). Therefore, most individuals with knee OA experience continuously worsening symptoms until severity which requires total knee arthroplasty (TKA), an invasive surgical intervention replacing damaged structures in the knee, which usually occurs after 9–12 years of knee OA symptom onset (Crawford et al., 2013; London et al., 2011; Evans et al., 2019).

Conservative interventions must begin as early in the development of knee OA as possible, or else TKA will become essential for symptomatic relief later in its progression (Hsu and Siwiec, 2024; Pelletier et al., 2023). Patients who meet the criteria for TKA but either refuse or cannot access it fall into the “treatment gap”, a period where patients experience severe pain, decreased quality of life, and heavy financial burdens (London et al., 2011).

1.2. Diagnostic imaging procedures and grading scales

Knee OA severity is primarily assessed based on joint space narrowing in the knee and damage to the knee-area bones (patella, tibia, and femur) and associated cartilage. These traits are typically assessed using radiographic (X-ray), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), or computed tomography (CT) imaging. Many grading scales exist for evaluating knee OA severity in affected patients. Kellgren–Lawrence and Ahlback scales are two of the most commonly used grading scales.

The Kellgren–Lawrence (KL) scale assesses OA on planar X-rays. The KL scale defines knee OA on a scale of 0 (normal) to 4 (severe) based on factors such as the presence of osteophytes, narrowing space between joints, presence of cysts and sclerosis, and contour deformities on bone ends (Hx et al., 2014). A KL grade of 2 or more confirms OA diagnosis.

The Ahlback grading system is also used on planar X-rays of the knee. This system classifies knee OA on a scale from 0 (no OA) to 5 (bone defect/loss > 10 mm with severe partial dislocation of knee bones), focusing on joint space narrowing and irregular bone contact in the knee (Martins et al., 2017).

While commonly used, both the KL and Ahlback grading scales are criticized due to opportunities for subjective interpretation in use of the scales. Often, KL results are considered unreliable due to inexact wording of the descriptors within the classification system that define each grade (Schiphof et al., 2008; Hayes et al., 2016). Ahlback grades are widely criticized for low and inconsistent levels of inter-observer agreement regarding scale classifications, which can be heavily based on knee positioning in the radiographs (Martins et al., 2017; Galli et al.,

2003). Between KL and Ahlback grading, KL has higher inter- and intra-observer reliability (Holzer et al., 2015); however, the two grading systems demonstrate high correlations of 0.76–0.78 (Pettersson et al., 1997).

1.3. Use of machine learning for knee osteoarthritis assessment

Machine learning (ML), or the study of how computer algorithms can learn from large data sets and produce models that demonstrate relationships and influences on an item of interest (Kokkotis et al., 2020), has a prominent role in modern medical imaging practice. This can be applied to classification and treatment planning for knee OA. ML models have already successfully been employed to predict symptomatic, radiographic, MRI, and surgical requirement outcomes (Joseph et al., 2003). Many classification and regression models, deep learning convolutional neural networks, and feature engineering techniques like principal component analysis (PCA) have been trained on medical images of patients with knee OA to classify and assess the severity of the disease, with accuracy scores ranging from 75% to 92% (Kokkotis et al., 2020; Ashinsky et al., 2017; Marques et al., 2013; Abedin et al., 2019; Donoghue et al., 2011; Yaodong Du et al., 2018). Table 1 summarizes these previous research results, indicating the type of input data, ML models used, and performance scores. The progression of OA can also be predicted using ML algorithms on X-ray images and other general patient health information, with AUC and F1 scores of 79% across two different studies (Y. Du et al., 2018; Tiulpin et al., 2019).

Recent advances in ML models for knee OA assessment highlight the benefits of using multimodal data (Joseph et al., 2003). A recent study by Rajamohan et al. (2023) assessed the singular or combined performance of MRI imaging, radiographic data, and clinical risk factor data to predict which patients (n = 706) in the Osteoarthritis Initiative cohort (Lester et al., 2006) would advance to TKA. Models which received MRI and radiographic data (AUC = 0.90) performed better than any singular input model (AUC = 0.77–0.89). The input of CT images alongside the evaluation of MRI images by ML models brings a great potential benefit to ML-guided assessment of knee OA.

1.4. Segmentation accuracy in knee cartilage imaging

Accurate segmentation of knee cartilage is a critical prerequisite for reliable quantitative imaging analysis, yet even state-of-the-art methods exhibit boundary variability that must be accounted for. Numerous MRI-based validation studies report that cartilage thickness and surface segmentation errors are typically sub-millimetric. Optical-scan comparison studies reported mean absolute cartilage surface errors of approximately 0.67 mm, corresponding to about two pixels at a 0.39 mm resolution (Broeck et al., 2013). Fully automatic 3D MRI analyses achieve interscan thickness errors of 0.03–0.21 mm (Sekiya et al., 2021), and large osteoarthritis cohorts show that 93% of regional thickness measurements differ by no more than 0.20 mm between repeated scans (Katano et al., 2025). Deep-learning segmentation models for cartilage morphology report thickness biases of roughly –0.12 to 0.33 mm (Kessler et al., 2022), while classical and learning-based cartilage quantification methods similarly show thickness errors in the 0.12–0.31 mm range across protocols (Cohen et al., 1999; Fripp et al., 2010). Additional benchmark studies on knee MRI segmentation confirm that high-quality approaches frequently achieve sub-voxel errors, often below 0.2 mm in favorable regions, though peripheral and thin cartilage can exhibit larger deviations (Yao et al., 2023; Ebrahimkhani et al., 2020). Collectively, these findings indicate that realistic cartilage segmentation variability generally lies in the 0.1–0.3 mm range for thickness and local surface error, with some protocols exhibiting values up to approximately 0.6–0.7 mm.

Table 1

Review of previous studies for knee OA prediction/regression. Adapted from Kokkotis et al. (2020). KL = Kellgren–Lawrence, JSM = joint space mapping.

Author	Data	Feature engineering	Learning algorithm	Validation	Results
Abedin et al. (2019)	Questionnaire/X-ray	LASSO	Elastic Net, RF, CNN	70/30 split	RMSE: CNN 0.77, EN 0.97, RF 0.94
Ashinsky et al. (2017)	MRI	–	WN(D-CHRM) Classifier	Leave-One-Out CV	75% accuracy
Donoghue et al. (2011)	MRI	Laplacian Eigenmap	Linear Regression	External validation (270 knees)	R^2 up to 0.75
Yaodong Du et al. (2018)	MRI	PCA	ANN, SVM, RF, Naïve Bayes	10-fold CV	AUC: ANN 0.761, RF 0.785
Marques et al. (2013)	MRI	Texture + PLS	FLDA	10F-CV + 10% holdout	AUC = 0.92
Pedoia et al. (2018)	MRI + biomechanics	Topological Data Analysis	Logistic Regression	–	AUC = 83.8%

1.5. Research aims and objectives

The goal of this study is to evaluate the robustness of multimodal CT-MRI-derived cartilage biomarkers for knee OA classification under controlled segmentation inaccuracies, following a cartilage segmentation protocol previously established in F.K. Ciliberti et al. (2022), Aubonnet et al. (2022). The precision of these manual segmentations might not be consistently replicable in all clinical settings. There is a gap in the knowledge of how outcomes will differ if this process is automated or manually replicated with technique error (poor segmentation) or equipment error (low-quality images). Therefore, the objectives of this work are:

1. to demonstrate that the extracted features are able to reliably distinguish between degenerative knees and control ones.
2. to evaluate the sensitivity of these features and of the associated machine learning models to controlled segmentation inaccuracies, thereby assessing whether highly precise manual segmentation is strictly necessary for reliable knee OA classification.

2. Methods

The workflow of this study is illustrated in Fig. 1. Starting from CT and MRI scans of different knee types and from cartilages segmented on the MRI and next registered on CT, the idea is to introduce controlled segmentation errors to mimic a more realistic environment. After that, inferential statistics and ML analysis will be used to test knee OA classification performance with data containing slightly altered pixel boundaries. In this way, the robustness of the extracted parameters and ML classification models can be evaluated under segmentation inaccuracies.

2.1. RESTORE and SINPAIN dataset - participants

Participants were recruited as part of the European projects RESTORE (<https://restoreproject.eu/>) (RESTORE Consortium, 2024) and SINPAIN (<https://www.osteoarthritis-SINPAIN.eu/>) (SINPAIN Consortium, 2024). The aim of RESTORE is to implement patient-specific solutions for cartilage regeneration. The aim of SINPAIN is to develop advanced siRNA therapies to create safe, efficient, and cost-effective treatment for knee OA, using machine-learning tools to support the delivery of personalized care. This study has been approved by the Icelandic Bioethics Commission (approval number: VSN-19-050).

After giving informed consent, 95 subjects (48 females, 47 males, age = 47.2 ± 18.0 (18–79)) underwent CT and MRI scans of one or both knees (for a total of 130 knee scans) at Landspítali University Hospital in Reykjavik, Iceland, using standardized acquisition protocols and patient positioning. Orthopedic doctors evaluated 51 knees as degenerative (D) (all coming from symptomatic subjects diagnosed

Table 2

Descriptive statistics for study participants: degenerative class (“D”; n = 42, 20 females, 22 males), control class (“C”, n = 53, 28 females, 25 males), and total sample (“T”; n = 95, 48 females, 47 males).

	Age	Height (m)	Weight (kg)	BMI
Min (D)	38	1.51	67	23.88
Max (D)	79	1.92	144	43.42
Mean (D)	62.14	1.74	92.40	30.48
St Dev (D)	10.11	0.10	17.08	5.17
Min (C)	18	1.59	46	17.97
Max (C)	67	1.94	120	39.18
Mean (C)	35.45	1.75	79.62	25.92
St Dev (C)	13.46	0.10	17.00	5.20
Min (T)	18	1.51	46	17.97
Max (T)	79	1.94	144	43.42
Mean (T)	47.25	1.75	85.27	27.94
St Dev (T)	17.95	0.10	18.11	5.64

with OA and with an Ahlback grade between 2–4), while 79 knees belong to healthy volunteers, with no prior history of degeneration or trauma, used as control (C) samples. Descriptive statistics of each class are available in Table 2.

2.2. CT and MRI imaging

While X-ray or “radiographic” imaging is a common technique used to diagnose knee OA (Geng et al., 2023), CT and MRI imaging can allow for an OA diagnosis before degeneration is evident in radiographic scans (Crues et al., 1991) via visualization of pathologic and tomographic changes in soft tissues, such as cartilage which is lost or damaged by knee OA. A combination of CT and MRI images was used as input data for this work.

The CT scanner used was a Toshiba Aquillion One, 320 slice, which covered a 16 cm area of interest in a single gantry rotation. Slice thickness was 0.5 mm with an increment of 0.25 mm. Tube voltage was 120 kV, tube current was 250 mA and effective mAs was 125. The protocol covered about 15 cm of area (axial plane) centered at the knee joint with small variations according to patient size. No intravenous contrast was administered. The initial CT dose index was set to 12.1 mGy. The preliminary dose-length product was 193.2 mGy*cm. These values were individually recalculated by the CT scanner for each patient according to size/thickness of the examined area (F.K. Ciliberti et al., 2022).

The MRI scanner was a 3T Siemens Healthcare Prisma scanner. Volumetric 3D sequences with isotropic voxels of 0.6 mm were acquired in the axial plane with a surface coil without intravenous contrast. This allowed for reconstructions in various planes along regions of interest. A 3D fast spin echo, intermediate weighted and fat-suppressed sequence which allowed for morphologic evaluation of cartilage and for better assessment of subchondral bone marrow was used. The maximum field

Fig. 1. Workflow of the methods for cartilage segment modification and ML classification.

of view was 16 cm, with a minimum matrix size of 256×256 . The area of interest was cartilage-covered areas around the knee. The protocol covered 14 cm centered at the knee joint (F.K. Ciliberti et al., 2022).

2.3. Image processing and feature extraction

The first aim of the study was to assert that the extracted parameters could serve as a reliable basis for knee OA classification. To achieve this, segmentations were performed for the femoral, patellar, lateral tibial, and medial tibial cartilages on each patient's knee, with radiometric features extracted for classification purposes in the ML models of choice.

CT and MRI images from all patients were uploaded into Materialise MIMICS software (Materialise Interactive Medical Image Control System, Materialise, Belgium) (Materialise, 2024), a medical modeling software used to analyze and model three-dimensional (3D) anatomical shapes from two-dimensional (2D) medical images (Materialise, 2024). Four types of knee cartilage were investigated: femoral cartilage (femcart), patellar cartilage (patcart), lateral tibial cartilage (lattibcart) and medial tibial cartilage (medtibcart).

Cartilage masks were manually segmented from MRI images, which is most suitable for soft tissue visualization (F.K. Ciliberti et al., 2022; Aubonnet et al., 2022). Segmentations were performed by multiple operators with technical expertise in medical image processing, following a shared segmentation protocol established within the project. All segmentations were subsequently reviewed and supervised by experienced operators to ensure anatomical consistency across subjects. In cases where inconsistencies were identified, segmentations were refined or re-segmented during the supervision step to homogenize the segmentation pipeline across operators.

To enable the study of CT-based radiodensity from MRI-segmented cartilage, MRI and CT images were spatially aligned using a landmark-based registration approach implemented in Materialise Mimics software. CT images were defined as the fixed image, while MRI images were treated as the moving image. MRI and CT acquisitions were performed with the patient in the same physical position, which facilitated anatomical correspondence between modalities. At least four

anatomical landmarks were manually selected (e.g., superior/inferior patellar points in the sagittal plane, tibial tuberosity superior point, and a lateral tibial point in the coronal plane), and the resulting rigid transform was applied to the MRI and its segmentations. After alignment, a Maximum Gray Value (Max GV) fusion was used to combine MRI and CT intensities, and minor manual adjustments were performed when needed to refine cartilage positioning relative to bone.

Minor manual adjustments of the cartilage masks were performed, including a density threshold of 0 to 300 Hounsfield units (HU). HU are a measurement of radiodensity automatically calculated from CT image pixel gray values. HU values are calculated using the following formula:

$$HU = 1000 \times \frac{\mu - \mu_{\text{water}}}{\mu_{\text{water}}} \quad (1)$$

where μ is the linear attenuation coefficient of the material, and μ_{water} is the linear attenuation coefficient of water. Bones have values of > 300 HU, whereas cartilage HU values typically fall between 60–140 but increase towards 300 HU as aging cartilage calcifies (Radiopaedia.org contributors, 2024; RESTORE Project, 2021).

Quantitative evaluation of registration accuracy was limited by the absence of voxel-level ground-truth annotations. Therefore, all registrations were visually inspected and validated by an experienced musculoskeletal radiologist. The assessment focused on anatomical plausibility, alignment of cartilage and bone surfaces across MRI and CT, and absence of observable misregistration artifacts.

The same methodology has been previously described in previous works (F.K. Ciliberti et al., 2022; Aubonnet et al., 2022). The following properties were extracted: mean and standard deviation HU density values from the mask, and surface area (mm^2) and volume (mm^3) from corresponding three-dimensional (3D) parts (Table 3), for a total of 16 features.

2.4. Imitating automatic/manual error

The second aim of the study was to determine whether or not the extensive manual labor and expertise required for precise cartilage segmentations would be necessary to use the original image analysis

Table 3
Features extracted from cartilage masks in MIMICS.

Cartilage mask	Features
Femoral	Average Density (HU) Standard Deviation Density (HU) Volume (mm ³) Surface Area (mm ²)
Patellar	Average Density (HU) Standard Deviation Density (HU) Volume (mm ³) Surface Area (mm ²)
Tibial (Lateral)	Average Density (HU) Standard Deviation Density (HU) Volume (mm ³) Surface Area (mm ²)
Tibial (Medial)	Average Density (HU) Standard Deviation Density (HU) Volume (mm ³) Surface Area (mm ²)

procedure of CT/MRI to identify OA. Therefore, two study objectives were identified: to imitate automated error (as if, in an automated process, an image analysis ML model were to extract cartilage mask and part segments with boundaries expanded or dilated by one or many pixels), and to imitate manual error (similar to automated error, but with holes filled in, as to mimic what might be created by an individual with little experience in segmentation or an untrained eye for cartilage boundaries). Both of these errors might also occur due to equipment error, such as low quality or blurry images.

To manipulate images within the MIMICS software, all masks were uploaded onto MIMICS and subject to “erosion” (erode), “dilation” (dilate), “opening” (open), and “closing” (close) operations (or combinations of the operations) using the Morphological Functions tool with 8-connectivity dilation or erosion. A spherical structural element was used to perform the morphological operations. The erode function eliminates the outer boundary of a mask of the number of pixels selected, whereas the dilate function extends the boundary of the mask. The open function performs an erode followed by a dilate to break small connections in the mask. The close function performs a dilate followed by an open, filling cavities within a mask. In digital morphology, “connectivity” refers to how neighboring pixels (in 2D: 4- or 8-connectivity; in 3D: 6-, 18-, or 26-connectivity) are defined as adjacent during morphological propagation. In our workflow, MIMICS applies 8-connectivity slice-wise, which determines how the structuring element interacts with the mask during erosion, dilation, opening, and closing (Materialise NV, 2020). The erode and dilate functions used individually can mimic automated error by expanding or reducing mask boundaries without filling in holes created by these operations. Using erode and dilate operations in tandem with close operation will fill in holes to better simulate manual error.

In our CT data, one pixel corresponds to approximately 0.3 mm in-plane, and therefore a one-pixel morphological operation reflects a realistic displacement scale for boundary uncertainty in knee cartilage segmentation. Moreover, the results returned when the morphological operations were applied on our data using 2 or more pixels were deemed improbable to occur in clinical settings by visual inspection. Therefore, the operations were only performed to the expanse of one pixel’s 8-connectivity. The final modifications used to imitate automatic and manual errors are described in Table 4 and visualized in Figs. 2 (for D samples) and 3 (C samples). The same 16 features extracted from the original mask (Table 3) were also obtained from these modified segmentations.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Inferential statistics were initially used to analyze significant differences between classes D and C. For each feature, we evaluated the

Fig. 2. Examples of “Original” (center), “Dilate 1” (left), and “Erode 1” cartilage masks and three-dimensional parts for a patient with knee OA (Class: “Degenerative” (D)).

Fig. 3. Examples of “Original” (center), “Dilate 1” (left), and “Erode 1” cartilage masks and three-dimensional parts for a healthy patient (Class: “Control” (C)).

Table 4
Mask modifications using morphological functions in MIMICS.

Operation	Purpose
Erode 1	Erosion (Automated)
Dilate 1	Dilation (Automated)
Close 1 then Erode 1	Erosion (Manual)
Dilate 1 then Close 1	Dilation (Manual)

differences between these two classes using a permutation test (Holt and Sullivan, 2023). This non-parametric method does not rely on any specific assumptions about the distribution of the data. The test statistic was defined as the difference in means between the two classes. Class labels were randomly shuffled 10000 times to generate a null distribution, and the p -value was calculated as the proportion of permutations where the test statistic was at least as extreme as the observed value. This procedure was applied to the original dataset as well as to the four datasets generated with simulated segmentation errors, in order to assess the robustness of the results.

2.6. Machine learning processes

ML models were implemented for knee OA classification from both original and modified mask segmentations and correspondent three-dimensional parts.

2.6.1. Data preprocessing

The target variable (“Category”) from each individual was binarized, setting subjects in class “D” (degenerative) equal to 1 and “C” (control) subjects to 0. One patient in class “D” had all pixels in the medial tibial cartilage mask eliminated with the use of “Erode 1” and “Close 1 Erode 1” modifications. This instance was removed from “Erode 1” and “Close 1 Erode 1” modification data sets. The final data set input into ML models contained 79 instances in class “C” and 50 or 51 in class “D”.

All quantitative input features were standardized using `scikit-learn StandardScaler()` z-score normalization. This normalization accounts for scaling influence, which some ML models used in this work (logistic regression and support vector machines) are sensitive towards.

2.6.2. ML models

Six ML models were evaluated on the data. Three of the six selected models are tree-based: Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Gradient Boosting (GB). DT is the simplest tree model, creating one tree with binary or multi-way splits based on feature thresholds (Rokach and Maimon, 2001). RF is a tree-based ensemble that uses “bagging” to train trees in parallel and makes decisions based on average or majority decisions from the individual trees (Breiman, 2001). GB is another tree-based ensemble method, but trains individual trees sequentially, correcting residuals (errors) for each tree and computing the results from the “strongest predictor” which is built from the ensemble of individual decision trees (Friedman, 2001). DT and GB can be sensitive to overfitting, but RF’s final step of averaging ensemble results reduces this risk. All tree node splits were binary, which is the default setting of the `scikit-learn` package used to access the models.

Two of the ML models selected for this work were types of Support Vector Machine (SVM), one linear (LinearSVC) and one with non-linear radial basis function (RBF) kernel (RBF Support Vector Classifier). SVM is a ML model which attempts to locate the line or plane that maximizes space between separated groups in a classification problem and the SVM decision “margin” (`scikit-learn developers, 2024b`). LinearSVM performs this on a two-dimensional plane. RBF Support Vector Classifier is able to capture more complex margins by elevating data to a higher-dimensional space, finding the plane margin in the higher dimension, and bringing both the data and margin back to the original plane for a non-linear decision margin without ever transforming the data. This is called the “kernel trick”. SVM models generally have a low risk of overfitting, unless C and gamma values are too high.

The final ML model selected was Logistic Regression with Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) regularization (LR). Logistic regression is a model that makes binary classifications based on a sigmoid (logistic) function. Adding L1, or “LASSO”, regularization reduces the weights of some attributes to zero, allowing the model to become simpler and avoid overfitting or feature redundancy (`scikit-learn developers, 2024a`). The presence of overfitting and underfitting is heavily dependent on the choice of “C”, the inverse of the regularization factor.

2.6.3. Model training and hyperparameter tuning

All ML analyses were carried out using nested cross-validation (nested CV), a two-layered validation approach that separates model selection from model evaluation (Krstajic et al., 2014). In the inner loop, hyperparameter optimization was performed with `GridSearchCV` using stratified k-fold cross-validation (k=5). Hyperparameter grids for each model were predefined, and the inner loop extensively searched these grids to identify the combination yielding the highest cross-validation accuracy within each fold. The outer loop of nested CV then provided an unbiased estimate of model performance on unseen data. This approach is particularly important in biomedical applications, where datasets are often small and the risk of overfitting is high, ensuring a more reliable estimate of generalization performance.

Using the optimized hyperparameters selected in the inner loop, model performance was evaluated in the outer loop of nested CV. Performance metrics included accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and the Receiver Operating Characteristic-Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC).

3. Results

3.1. Statistical analysis

Table 5 presents the p-values computed for both the original and modified datasets. Notably, the standard deviations of the densities maintained significant p-values across all datasets, despite the pixel modifications. The medial tibial cartilage volume and surface also remained significant across the datasets. However, the results were different for other features: the surface area of the femoral cartilage, the volume of the patellar cartilage, and the average HU density of the medial tibial cartilage were significant in the original dataset, but only some of the modified datasets retained these significant results. Certain features showed significance only in specific modified datasets; for instance, ‘PatCart Surface’ was significant only in the Erode1 dataset, and ‘LatTibCart Surface’ was significant only for the Dilate1 dataset. Meanwhile, ‘FemCart Volume’ was significant in the Erode1, Dilate1, and Dilate1Close1 datasets but not in the original dataset.

3.2. Machine learning performances

All ML analyses were performed on the Original Dataset as well as on the four datasets simulating automatic and manual errors. 5-fold nested cross-validation returned the optimized hyperparameters tuned on the inner folds.

Model performances were evaluated, and results are reported as the mean and standard deviation of the scores across the k=5 outer folds. For all performance metrics reviewed in this section, the highest score for each performance metric out of the applied ML models is in **bold**.

3.2.1. Original dataset

The evaluation of ML models on the Original Dataset yielded promising results. Results are reported in Table 6. Among all models, the RBF Support Vector Classifier achieved the highest scores in all the metrics, indicating strong overall performance. Using the F1 Weighted score as a benchmark, the second best model was Linear SVC, which reached 0.80 ± 0.11 . The tree-based models (GB, DT and RF) all showed similar performances, each reaching an F1 Weighted score around 0.77. Although this represents a drop of approximately 10 percentage points compared to the best performing, their results remain robust and acceptable.

3.2.2. Pixel Erode 1

Erode1, the first ‘automated’ error introduced, was applied as a one-pixel erosion to the cartilage masks of 130 patients. Out of these, 129 patients (79 in class “C” and 50 in class “D”) retained all their cartilage masks after the modification. However, one patient in class “D” lost all remaining pixels in their medial tibial cartilage mask as a result of the modification.

The ML evaluated on the dataset, including the features extracted from the eroded masks, did not reach the same scores as the original dataset, but still returned relatively high performance metric scores. The highest weighted F1 score for Erode1 data sets was 0.83 ± 0.04 for the LinearSVC model. Although this score is lower than the best model’s score on the original dataset, it was still higher than the score obtained by the same model on the original dataset. LR and RBF SVC also recorded similarly high scores. RF and GB models achieved scores similar to those on the original dataset, with a weighted F1 score of 0.78. DT model performed the worst across all metrics. (Table 7)

Table 5
p-values for Original, Erode1, Dilate1, Close1Erode1, and Dilate1Close1 datasets, rounded to 3 significant digits; significant values highlighted in **bold italic**.

Feature	p-values				
	Original	Erode1	Dilate1	Close1Erode1	Dilate1Close1
FemCart Avg Density	0.919	0.825	0.034*	0.000***	0.031*
FemCart StDev Density	0.000***	0.000***	0.001**	0.000***	0.001**
FemCart Volume	0.245	0.005**	0.001**	0.331	0.000***
FemCart Surface	0.000***	0.299	0.000***	0.178	0.000***
PatCart Avg Density	0.987	0.938	0.400	0.006**	0.361
PatCart StDev Density	0.000***	0.000***	0.001**	0.000***	0.001**
PatCart Volume	0.000***	0.000***	0.077	0.000***	0.100
PatCart Surface	0.654	0.000***	0.424	0.045*	0.684
MedTibCart Avg Density	0.019*	0.003**	0.191	0.796	0.200
MedTibCart StDev Density	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
MedTibCart Volume	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
MedTibCart Surface	0.011*	0.000***	0.037*	0.000***	0.034*
LatTibCart Avg Density	0.103	0.148	0.552	0.785	0.533
LatTibCart StDev Density	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
LatTibCart Volume	0.092	0.000***	0.492	0.065	0.530
LatTibCart Surface	0.310	0.142	0.116	0.566	0.148

* p < 0.05,
** p < 0.005,
*** p < 0.001.

Table 6
Performance metrics of different models on the Original Dataset, best model score for each metric in bold.

Model	Original dataset					
	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Weighted	ROC AUC
LinearSVC	0.80 ± 0.10	0.77 ± 0.15	0.73 ± 0.17	0.85 ± 0.12	0.80 ± 0.11	0.89 ± 0.07
RBF Support Vector Classifier	0.86 ± 0.07	0.87 ± 0.12	0.78 ± 0.12	0.91 ± 0.09	0.86 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.06
Logistic Regression	0.78 ± 0.10	0.76 ± 0.15	0.67 ± 0.17	0.86 ± 0.11	0.78 ± 0.10	0.87 ± 0.08
Decision Tree	0.78 ± 0.09	0.75 ± 0.16	0.67 ± 0.12	0.85 ± 0.09	0.77 ± 0.09	0.78 ± 0.09
Random Forest	0.78 ± 0.05	0.79 ± 0.13	0.63 ± 0.19	0.88 ± 0.10	0.77 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.08
Gradient Boosting	0.78 ± 0.12	0.77 ± 0.19	0.61 ± 0.19	0.89 ± 0.09	0.77 ± 0.12	0.84 ± 0.11

Table 7
Performance metrics of different models on the Erode1 Dataset, best model score for each metric in bold.

Model	Erode1					
	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Weighted	ROC AUC
LinearSVC	0.83 ± 0.04	0.82 ± 0.11	0.74 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.08	0.83 ± 0.04	0.86 ± 0.04
RBF Support Vector Classifier	0.81 ± 0.07	0.79 ± 0.11	0.72 ± 0.07	0.87 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.06	0.86 ± 0.07
Logistic Regression	0.82 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.12	0.74 ± 0.05	0.87 ± 0.09	0.82 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.04
Decision Tree	0.71 ± 0.06	0.63 ± 0.08	0.64 ± 0.14	0.75 ± 0.10	0.70 ± 0.06	0.72 ± 0.06
Random Forest	0.78 ± 0.05	0.76 ± 0.12	0.70 ± 0.11	0.84 ± 0.12	0.78 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.06
Gradient Boosting	0.78 ± 0.10	0.72 ± 0.14	0.76 ± 0.05	0.79 ± 0.16	0.78 ± 0.09	0.86 ± 0.06

Table 8
Performance metrics of different models on the Dilate1 Dataset, best model score for each metric in bold.

Model	Dilate1					
	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Weighted	ROC AUC
LinearSVC	0.80 ± 0.07	0.75 ± 0.12	0.75 ± 0.13	0.84 ± 0.08	0.80 ± 0.07	0.90 ± 0.06
RBF Support Vector Classifier	0.82 ± 0.06	0.80 ± 0.13	0.72 ± 0.08	0.87 ± 0.09	0.81 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.07
Logistic Regression	0.79 ± 0.08	0.75 ± 0.12	0.75 ± 0.15	0.82 ± 0.10	0.79 ± 0.08	0.90 ± 0.06
Decision Tree	0.58 ± 0.07	0.46 ± 0.12	0.49 ± 0.16	0.65 ± 0.06	0.58 ± 0.07	0.57 ± 0.09
Random Forest	0.76 ± 0.04	0.77 ± 0.07	0.57 ± 0.11	0.89 ± 0.05	0.75 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.08
Gradient Boosting	0.73 ± 0.07	0.70 ± 0.16	0.57 ± 0.11	0.84 ± 0.08	0.72 ± 0.07	0.82 ± 0.07

3.2.3. Pixel Dilate 1

Dilate1 is the other automated error introduced. In this case, no samples were lost; therefore, the new dataset still comprises 130 subjects. Table 8 shows that the best model remains RBF SVC on most of the metrics, maintaining a high score of 0.81 ± 0.06 on F1. Linear SVC reached performances similar to the ones in the Original dataset (0.80), while LR was slightly higher (0.79). All the other models scored lower results with respect to the original dataset (even if RF showed the highest specificity of the dataset, but only slightly higher than the original one and at the expense of a pretty low sensitivity). Also in this case, DT had the lower scores, not reaching 0.6 in most of the metrics.

3.2.4. Pixel Close 1 Erode 1

Close1Erode1 is a manual simulated error, composed by a closing operation followed by an erosion on all the segmented cartilages. Even in this case, due to the applied erosion, one ‘D’ sample lost all pixels and was removed. Results on this new dataset are shown in Table 9. Also in this case, RBF SVC reaches the highest score on all the metrics, with an F1 of 0.84, only 2 percentage points lower than the original data set, and with less variability across folds (StDev = 0.02 versus 0.07 in the original data set). In this case, RF is the second best model, reaching a F1 of 0.81 ± 0.06, comparable to the highest outcomes of the original

Table 9

Performance metrics of different models on the Close1Erode1 Dataset, best model score for each metric in bold.

Close1Erode1						
Model	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Weighted	ROC AUC
LinearSVC	0.77 ± 0.06	0.74 ± 0.13	0.68 ± 0.07	0.83 ± 0.09	0.77 ± 0.06	0.85 ± 0.06
RBF Support Vector Classifier	0.84 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.10	0.78 ± 0.10	0.89 ± 0.07	0.84 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.04
Logistic Regression	0.79 ± 0.06	0.73 ± 0.10	0.76 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.08	0.79 ± 0.06	0.86 ± 0.04
Decision Tree	0.71 ± 0.07	0.61 ± 0.06	0.62 ± 0.19	0.76 ± 0.02	0.70 ± 0.07	0.73 ± 0.09
Random Forest	0.81 ± 0.06	0.76 ± 0.10	0.76 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.06	0.88 ± 0.06
Gradient Boosting	0.79 ± 0.11	0.73 ± 0.13	0.72 ± 0.17	0.84 ± 0.08	0.79 ± 0.11	0.86 ± 0.08

Table 10

Performance metrics of different models on the Dilate1Close1 Dataset, best model score for each metric in bold.

Dilate1Close1						
Model	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Weighted	ROC AUC
LinearSVC	0.81 ± 0.06	0.78 ± 0.09	0.73 ± 0.11	0.86 ± 0.07	0.81 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.05
RBF Support Vector Classifier	0.80 ± 0.07	0.78 ± 0.14	0.70 ± 0.11	0.86 ± 0.10	0.80 ± 0.07	0.90 ± 0.07
Logistic Regression	0.82 ± 0.08	0.78 ± 0.10	0.75 ± 0.19	0.86 ± 0.07	0.81 ± 0.09	0.92 ± 0.05
Decision Tree	0.68 ± 0.06	0.60 ± 0.10	0.49 ± 0.19	0.80 ± 0.06	0.66 ± 0.07	0.65 ± 0.09
Random Forest	0.79 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.11	0.59 ± 0.13	0.93 ± 0.06	0.78 ± 0.07	0.86 ± 0.05
Gradient Boosting	0.75 ± 0.11	0.69 ± 0.13	0.67 ± 0.19	0.81 ± 0.09	0.75 ± 0.11	0.79 ± 0.10

dataset, but significantly better than the same algorithm applied to that dataset. Worst model is again DT, with 0.70 ± 0.07 of F1.

3.2.5. Pixel Dilate 1 Close 1

The other manual simulated error is given by a dilation of 1 pixel followed by a closing operation of 1 pixel. For this simulated error, Table 10 displays different trends than the other data sets. Although the RBF SVC maintains high performance, the best weighted F1 score was achieved by LinearSVC, with a value of 0.81 ± 0.06 . Additionally, linearSVC produced the highest ROC AUC of 0.92 ± 0.05 . This score is not only the highest for this dataset, but also the highest overall, including results from the Original dataset. LR reached the highest accuracy and sensitivity for this dataset, while RF reached the highest precision and specificity, but again at the expense of a pretty low sensitivity. DT is confirmed as the model with the lowest scores.

4. Discussion

4.1. Impact of simulated segmentation errors on statistical significance

The results in Table 5 illustrate how cartilage features respond to segmentation perturbations introduced by morphological operators (Erode1, Dilate1, Close1Erode1, and Dilate1Close1). Comparing these datasets with the original allows us to distinguish between features that remain stable despite boundary errors and those that are more sensitive to segmentation accuracy. Overall, the analysis confirms that even minimal boundary shifts — on the order of a single pixel — can alter statistical significance across features and cartilage areas.

Among the evaluated features, cartilage density variation (StDev) was the most robust. It consistently yielded highly significant results (p -values ≤ 0.001) across all compartments and perturbations, indicating that density heterogeneity is largely unaffected by segmentation variability. This stability highlights StDev as a reliable biomarker, even when segmentations are imperfect. In contrast, average density showed greater variability. For example, femoral cartilage average density, non-significant in the Original dataset, became significant after dilation or closing-based perturbations. This likely reflects the inclusion of adjacent voxels with different intensities: the modified datasets might include bone structures (and therefore increasing average HU values) in the D cases, especially in the regions where bones are in closer contact due to the disease; another option, on the contrary, is that the modified segmentations might include fluid accumulation (with HU close to 0), that reflects the inflammation of D cases.

Morphometric features (volume and surface area) were generally more susceptible to segmentation errors. Several became significant

only under perturbed conditions. For instance, PatCart Surface was non-significant in the Original dataset but highly significant after erosion, while FemCart Volume gained significance following erosion and dilation. These patterns suggest that minor boundary modifications can artificially enhance statistical differences. Conversely, features such as FemCart Surface lost significance under erosion, underlining the importance of boundary voxels for shape-dependent measures. Cartilage volume and surface measures have indeed been proven as strong predictors of knee OA progression. Imaging assessments of cartilage volume, thickness, and surface area reliably predict both structural changes and symptoms, with ML further improving accuracy (Schaefer et al., 2017; Panfilov et al., 2021; F. Ciliberti et al., 2022; Maruotto et al., 2025). In fact, the volume of patellar cartilage was also found to be highly significant and remained significant even when accounting for erosion, indicating its resilience to voxel loss. However, this significance was lost after dilation, likely due to the inclusion of non-cartilage tissue. This suggests that the overestimation caused by dilation has a more destabilizing effect than the underestimation resulting from erosion. The medial tibial cartilage displayed consistently significant results across nearly all features and perturbations: this robustness suggests that the medial compartment may serve as a particularly sensitive biomarker region, where disease-related alterations manifest more reliably and are less confounded by segmentation variability. In contrast, the lateral tibial cartilage was the most variable, with average density and surface area remaining largely unaffected across all datasets. It is known that the medial knee compartment is the most predictive in OA because it is most commonly affected because of the knee biomechanics, as the medial compartment bears more load during gait, making it more prone to degeneration and OA progression; isolated medial tibiofemoral OA occurs in about 27% of cases, far more than isolated lateral or patellofemoral OA (Stoddart et al., 2020; Herman and Giffin, 2016).

Overall, these findings highlight that the type of feature significantly impacts robustness against segmentation variability. Measures of density appear to be stable and reliable, while morphometric features are more susceptible to fluctuations caused by errors. Notably, the emergence of significance in perturbed datasets, as opposed to the Original ones, indicates a methodological risk: segmentation inconsistencies can lead to false positives or obscure genuine effects, depending on the anatomical region and feature in question. This underscores the importance of considering segmentation robustness when interpreting imaging biomarkers, especially for geometry-based measures such as volume and surface area.

Fig. 4. ROC curves of the four best models (Linear SVM, RBF SVM, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest) on the Original, Erode1, Dilate1, Close1Erode1, and Dilate1Close1 datasets.

4.2. Performance metrics amongst all ML models

One aim of our work is to identify the best ML models for knee OA classification using CT-MRI data on small datasets. In this discussion section, we will compare the performance of the tested models primarily on the basis of weighted F1 score.

The Radial Basis Function SVC model returned the best weighted F1 scores for the Original data set, Dilate1 and Close1Erode1 data sets, with F1 weighted scores for this model of 0.80 or greater for all data sets. Similar success was observed with Linear SVC, returning the highest F1 scores for Erode1 and Dilate1Close1 data sets. The high F1 scores returned by SVC models illustrate their ability to capture complexity within the input data and demonstrates their utility for image-based cartilage segmentation analysis, even on imprecise data.

LR achieved high scores across all models, returning the second or third highest F1 weighted score on all data sets. It is probable that the regularization feature helped reduce overfitting, contributing to the rise of F1 metric scores. RF models also consistently returned satisfactory results for F1 weighted score, particularly for manual error simulation data, but all F1 weighted scores were 0.75 or greater. These scores support the use of these models for knee OA classification.

GB models returned F1 scores between 0.72 and 0.79. However, with sensitivity scores as low as 0.57, it is clear that GB might be prone to higher instances of false negatives.

DT models returned the lowest F1 weighted scores of the tested models. Its highest scores were returned while interpreting the original data set, whereas simulated errors returned much lower scores, especially dilation errors. Compared to the other ML models, GB and DT were the least ideal models for knee OA classification.

Non-tree-based models (RBF SVC, SVC Linear, LR) outperformed tree-based models (DT, RF, GB) on sensitivity, ROC AUC, and accuracy scores. A tree-based model only produced higher average scores than a non-tree-based model for specificity and precision (RF over LR). However, the clinical significance of sensitivity and F1 scores must be considered with greater weight when comparing performances of the models, as priority should lie with avoiding occurrences of false negatives so as not to miss treatment opportunities for individuals with knee OA pathophysiology. Therefore, the non-tree-based models returned the greatest scores for the most important metrics in ML-based knee OA classification.

Fig. 4 shows a comparison among the ROC AUC curves of the four best models (Linear SVM, RBF SVM, LR, and RF) among the different datasets. Across these models, the ROC curves show consistently high true positive rates, suggesting that the classifiers can adapt to small segmentation perturbations, highlighting their robustness when dealing with imprecise data. Both SVC models exhibit strong performance across all datasets, with ROC curves clustering near the top-left corner. This indicates a high degree of stability under the applied morphological transformations of the segmentation. LR shows slightly more variation between datasets compared to SVCs. The ROC curves for eroded and dilated versions deviate more noticeably, suggesting that linear models may be somewhat sensitive to boundary changes in the input features. RF displays the most variation among the models. While performance is still strong, transformations in the data (particularly simulations of automated error) lead to small reductions in the true positive rate at moderate false positive rates, suggesting that RF-based classifications may be more sensitive to subtle changes in segmentation data.

4.3. Comparing simulated errors

4.3.1. Erosion vs dilation errors

Dilation errors typically had a stronger negative effect on performance metrics than erosion errors, particularly for F1 scores. This emphasizes the importance of accurately capturing the outer cartilage boundary in image-based ML classification: including too much tissue beyond the cartilage surface likely includes non-cartilage structures (such as fat, fluid or bone edges) that dilute OA-specific information and negatively impact model performance. Especially in terms of radiodensity, all these structures present different HU ranges (with fat arriving up to -100 HU and bone up to 1000 HU), that can therefore affect the ML models, even if only for few pixels. In contrast, erosion errors shift focus toward more central pixels, which may still contain meaningful information about inner-cartilage composition affected by OA pathophysiology. These observations support the idea that the cartilage surface is an informative region for OA-related degeneration, but also that small losses of boundary detail may be less harmful than small over-extensions into surrounding anatomical regions.

4.3.2. Manual vs automated errors

Manual and automated segmentation errors produced similar performance patterns for both erosion and dilation, with differences usually below 0.025 for erosion and 0.04 for dilation operations. This suggests that the results of this study can be applied to various clinic-based executions of image-based cartilage segmentations, whether these segmentations are produced by hand or using automated tools. The limited impact of small simulated errors in our study aligns with prior work comparing manual and automated knee cartilage segmentation. Modern deep-learning and hybrid methods typically achieve Dice coefficients of 0.82 – 0.93 , often approaching inter-reader variability (Zhang et al., 2023, 2022; Juras et al., 2020). Automated approaches also tend to slightly overestimate cartilage volume and thickness, but these biases are systematic and show strong linear correlations with manual measurements, allowing straightforward correction (Zhang et al., 2022; Juras et al., 2020; Fripp et al., 2010). Errors tend to increase in severe OA, where denuded bone, fissures, and joint effusion make cartilage more difficult to delineate (Zhang et al., 2023, 2022). Together, these findings support our observation that small boundary deviations — whether from erosion, dilation, or hole-filling — may not meaningfully disrupt downstream ML classification. The robustness of most models in our study mirrors that seen in morphometry, relaxometry, and OA progression research using automated segmentations.

4.3.3. Original dataset vs simulated errors datasets

Across all models, the original dataset returned the highest or near-highest performance scores (except for sensitivity), but differences between the original and simulated error sets were generally small (again with DT being the exception, especially under automated dilation). This pattern indicates that while precise cartilage segmentation yields optimal performance, the majority of tested ML models tolerate modest inaccuracies without major performance degradation. For most ML classifications, scores of 0.7 or more for any performance metric are considered adequate (Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009), although the stakes for correct classifications (especially of positive cases) are high in medical settings and higher scores are ideal, especially for sensitivity and F1 score. This suggests that automated segmentation pipelines could be viable even if they do not achieve perfect boundary accuracy, reducing the burden of manual correction. The methods reflect a reasonable simulation of error, as segmentation variability for osteoarthritis studies typically occurs between 0.1 – 0.3 mm for thickness and local surface error (Cohen et al., 1999; Fripp et al., 2010; Katano et al., 2025). However, larger boundary deviations or real-world segmentation (that are not as homogeneous as the ones performed in this study) may have stronger effects and should be evaluated in future studies. Expansion to a larger imaging data set will also be

necessary to fully determine generalizability and to validate whether these models can support OA classification in clinical environments. Overall, these findings indicate that the extracted CT- and MRI-based cartilage features provide stable and informative biomarkers for OA classification, even when segmentation imperfections are present. This resilience of the feature set further supports the feasibility of deploying these biomarkers in workflows where segmentation precision may vary.

4.4. Strengths, limitations, and future work

Although a wide range of image intensity, texture, or shape features could further enrich a multimodal analysis, the present study deliberately focuses on a compact set of features that are widely accessible in clinical workflows. Basic cartilage morphology (volume and surface area) and CT-derived radiodensity can be extracted directly from commercial medical imaging software (such as Mimics), without requiring extensive coding expertise, specialized radiomic toolboxes, or high-dimensional feature engineering. These features can also easily be interpreted by clinicians and radiologists. Our aim was therefore to assess the robustness of these simple and interpretable biomarkers to segmentation inaccuracies, rather than to maximize discriminative performance through extensive feature extraction. We note that a radiomics-based analysis of knee OA using a richer feature space has already been conducted in a previous work (Angelone et al., 2024), and the present study complements that work by addressing a different research question focused on segmentation robustness.

This study is strengthened by the use of multiple imaging inputs, which have previously been demonstrated to result in higher performances for ML models classifying knee OA than singular image-type input models (Rajamohan et al., 2023). The added value of the linked CT–MRI dataset lies in its ability to provide cartilage radiodensity measurements in HU, which are not obtainable from MRI-only datasets. Because cartilage cannot be segmented directly from CT due to limited soft-tissue contrast, the MRI-to-CT transfer of cartilage masks enables a unique investigation of how segmentation imprecision propagates into CT-based density biomarkers. This multimodal dependency cannot be reproduced using MRI-only datasets.

One strength of this work is the applicability of the methods to classify OA in other regions of the body. Although different risk factors might apply to the development of OA in the hips, spine, wrist, or other areas of the body, the pathophysiology apparent in CT and MRI images is similar in many ways (Martel-Pelletier et al., 2016). Therefore, the methods in this work could be generalized to the evaluation and classification of OA in different areas of the body.

The primary weakness of this work is the small sample size on which the analysis was performed. The test set size ($n = 23$ – 24) is inadequate to extrapolate these results to the estimated 595 million individuals diagnosed with knee OA annually (Steinmetz et al., 2023). These methods must be applied to larger data sets, ideally in the thousands or more, before they are recommended for clinical use.

Both a strengthening and a limiting aspect of the work is the use of MIMICS scripting to imitate automated or manual error. Only “erode”, “dilate”, “open” and “close” operators provided in MIMICS were used to modify cartilage masks. However, this limitation allowed for an identically sized set (relative to the original subject set) of imitated “errors” to be created.

ML models used in this project were all supervised learning models. Future applications of the data on unsupervised learning models could additionally be explored for use in clinical settings. In addition, we propose the incorporation of shape descriptors, radiomics, and possibly deep-learning-derived features to further expand the multimodal potential of this dataset.

Future research should aim to extend the validation of these findings on larger and more heterogeneous cartilage cohorts, incorporating segmentation data generated through both automated pipelines and manual user input to capture realistic variability. Moreover, expanding

the analysis to a wider range of ML techniques, including unsupervised and deep learning models, could provide a more comprehensive assessment of the robustness of imaging biomarkers across multiple joints and clinical settings, thereby moving beyond a knee-specific application.

5. Conclusions

Our work further supports the classification of knee OA using radiodensity and morphological measures of knee cartilage masks. They also imply that very high precision in segmenting cartilage masks might not be strictly necessary for successful ML-guided classification of knee OA from segmented CT and MRI images. Across all simulated segmentation inaccuracies, most ML models produced reliable and generalizable results, indicating that small variations at the cartilage boundary (on the order of one pixel) do not critically compromise classification performance. This is a key finding for clinical workflows in which segmentation quality may vary depending on operator expertise or automated pipelines. Among all tested models, SVMs (RBF and Linear kernels) consistently achieved the strongest and most stable performance across datasets, even when exposed to erosion/dilation operations. These models should therefore be considered primary candidates for future clinical application in knee OA classification. Future studies with larger datasets are necessary to validate these findings before clinical translation. However, our findings provide strong initial evidence that the proposed CT–MRI workflow and the selected ML models offer a robust and clinically promising strategy for knee OA classification.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sydney Fox: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Federica Kiyomi Ciliberti:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Halldór Jónsson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paolo Gargiulo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marco Recenti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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